

Comparative Evaluation of the Effectiveness of Methotrexate and Apremilast in the Treatment of Chronic Plaque Psoriasis

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Psoriasis is a chronic inflammatory skin disorder associated with significant morbidity. Despite the availability of various treatments, including Methotrexate and Apremilast, a clear comparison of their effectiveness in treating chronic plaque psoriasis remains essential for optimizing patient outcomes.

Aims & Objectives: This study aimed to evaluate and compare the therapeutic effects of Methotrexate and Apremilast in treating chronic plaque psoriasis, focusing on symptom improvement, PASI score reduction, and overall effectiveness.

Methods: An analytical study was conducted over one year at the Dermatology OPD of Rajshree Medical Research Institute, Bareilly. Patients aged 18-50 years with chronic plaque psoriasis were divided into two groups: Group 1 received Methotrexate, and Group 2 received Apremilast. Psoriasis severity was assessed using the Psoriasis Area and Severity Index (PASI) at baseline and monthly intervals for six months. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 26.0, with statistical tests including paired t-tests, ANOVA, and chi-square tests.

Results: The study found that Apremilast led to higher moderate improvement in scaling (70.4%) compared to Methotrexate (50%). By the PASI 6 stage, 92.5% of Apremilast patients achieved a PASI score below 15, compared to 76.92% of Methotrexate patients. Scalp involvement was more common in the Apremilast group (70.3%), while lower limb involvement was more prevalent in the Methotrexate group (42.3%).

Conclusions: Both Methotrexate and Apremilast were effective in managing chronic plaque psoriasis, with Apremilast showing a quicker reduction in disease severity. The choice of treatment may depend on specific symptoms and patient characteristics.

Keywords: Psoriasis; Methotrexate; Apremilast; PASI Score; Chronic Plaque Psoriasis.

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Introduction

Psoriasis is a chronic inflammatory skin disorder characterized by the formation of papulosquamous lesions, typically found on the extensor surfaces and scalp. [1] The severity of psoriasis varies widely, from a few scattered plaques to extensive body involvement. [2] Prevalence rates differ by region, with studies indicating a 2-3% prevalence in Europe and the United States, and approximately 0.47% in Asia.

Although the precise pathogenesis of psoriasis remains unclear, it is believed to result from a combination of environmental and hereditary factors. [3] Psoriasis is not just a skin condition; it is associated with a range of systemic issues, including malignancies, gastrointestinal, cardiac, and hepatobiliary diseases, and is often exacerbated by emotional and psychological stress. [4]

Treatment for psoriasis includes both topical and systemic therapies. Topical treatments commonly used are corticosteroids, vitamin D analogues, and phototherapy, while systemic treatments include

methotrexate, retinoids, cyclosporine, and biological agents. [5,6] Apremilast, a novel systemic therapy, has gained attention due to its mechanism as a phosphodiesterase 4 (PDE4) inhibitor, which elevates cAMP levels and modulates the inflammatory response in psoriasis.

Approved by the FDA in 2014, Apremilast is used for moderate-to-severe chronic plaque psoriasis in adults. [7,8] Methotrexate, a well-established treatment since the 1970s, inhibits DNA synthesis, thereby reducing skin cell turnover and plaque formation. Despite the availability of these therapies, there is a need to compare their effectiveness in treating chronic plaque psoriasis. [7,8] This study aims to evaluate and compare the therapeutic effects of Apremilast and Methotrexate, offering valuable insights to optimize treatment approaches and improve patient outcomes.

Materials & Methods

This analytical study was conducted over one year at the Dermatology Outpatient Department (OPD) of Rajshree Medical Research Institute, Bareilly. The study focused on patients aged 18-50 years with chronic plaque psoriasis lasting more than six months. Eligible participants were selected through convenient sampling and divided into two groups: Group 1 received methotrexate, and Group 2 received apremilast, following the department's treatment protocols. Exclusion criteria included pregnancy, lactation, BSA involvement of less than 10%, prior systemic treatment within the past year, systemic comorbidities, and inability to attend

follow-ups. Psoriasis severity was assessed using the Psoriasis Area and Severity Index (PASI) at baseline and monthly for six months. The study followed ethical guidelines, with informed consent from participants and Institutional Review Board approval. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 26.0, with paired t-tests for within-group improvements, ANOVA for between-group comparisons, and chi-square tests for adverse effects. Multiple regression analysis was used to adjust for confounding variables, ensuring a robust comparison of methotrexate and apremilast in treating chronic plaque psoriasis.

CONSORT Diagram

Figure 1: CONSORT Diagram

Results

Table 1: Comparison of Age and Gender Distribution in Methotrexate and Apremilast Treatment Groups

Category	Methotrexate (n)	Methotrexate %	Apremilast (n)	Apremilast %	P value
AGE GROUP					
18-25	6	23.07	3	11.1	
26-35	12	46.1	13	48.1	
36-45	7	26.9	9	33.3	0.83
46-50	1	3.93	2	7.5	
Total	26	100.0	27	100.0	
GENDER					
Male	19	73.1	15	70	0.73
Female	7	26.9	12	30	
Total	26	100.0	27	100.0	

Figure 2: Combined Distribution: Age group and gender (Methotrexate vs Apremilast)

Table 2: Comparison of Sites Involved and Aggravating Factors in Methotrexate and Apremilast Treatment Groups

Category	Methotrexate (n)	Apremilast (n)	% Methotrexate	% Apremilast
Sites Involved				
Scalp	13	19	50%	70.3%
Nails	0	2	0%	7.4%
Abdomen	4	3	15.3%	11.1%
Back	5	4	19.2%	14.8%
Upper Limb	2	2	7.6%	7.4%
Lower Limb	11	7	42.3%	25.9%
Palm and sole involvement	3	2	11.5%	7.4%
Aggravating Factors				
Alcohol	1	2	3.93%	7.4%
Smoking, Tobacco	1	2	3.93%	7.4%
Sunlight	1	1	3.93%	3.7%
Trauma	2	1	7.6%	3.7%
Food	1	2	3.93%	7.4%
No known aggravating factors	20	19	76.68%	70.4%
Total	26	27	100.0%	100.0%

Figure 3: Methotrexate vs Apremilast Frequencies

Table 3: Improvement in Psoriasis Symptoms for Methotrexate and Apremilast Treatment Groups

Symptom	Improvement Scale	Methotrexate (n)	Methotrexate (%)	Apremilast (n)	Apremilast (%)	p-value
Scaling	Slight Improvement	2	7.7%	3	11.1%	0.081
	Moderate Improvement	13	50.0%	19	70.4%	
	Marked Improvement	11	42.3%	5	18.5%	
Erythema	Slight Improvement	2	7.7%	2	7.4%	0.999
	Moderate Improvement	8	30.8%	7	25.9%	
	Marked Improvement	16	61.5%	18	66.7%	
Plaque	Slight Improvement	3	11.5%	5	18.5%	0.014
	Moderate Improvement	23	88.5%	22	81.5%	

Figure 4: Improvement of Symptoms for Methotrexate and Apremilast

Table 4: PASI Score Distribution across Different Stages in Methotrexate and Apremilast Treatment Groups

PASI Stage	PASI Range	Methotrexate (n)	Methotrexate (%)	Apremilast (n)	Apremilast (%)	P-Value
PASI 0	< 15	6	23.1%	4	14.8%	0.648
	16 - 25	4	15.4%	7	25.9%	
	> 25	16	61.5%	16	59.3%	
PASI 1	< 15	6	23.07%	4	14.8%	0.099
	16 - 25	6	23.07%	8	29.6%	
	> 25	14	53.86%	15	55.5%	
PASI 2	< 15	10	38.4%	6	22.2%	0.044
	16 - 25	10	38.4%	12	44.4%	
	> 25	6	23.2%	9	33.4%	
PASI 3	< 15	13	50%	16	59.3%	0.0065
	16 - 25	11	42.3%	11	40.7%	
	> 25	2	7.7%	0	0.0%	
PASI 4	< 15	18	69.2%	23	85.2%	0.028
	16 - 25	6	23.1%	4	14.8%	
	> 25	2	7.7%	0	0.0%	
PASI 6	< 15	20	76.92%	25	92.5%	0.005
	16 - 25	6	23.08%	2	7.5%	
	> 25	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	

Figure 5: PASI Stage comparison: Methotrexate and Apremilast

Table 5: PASI 75 (75% reduction)

Outcome	Methotrexate	Apremilast	P value
Achieved	17 (65.4%)	21 (77.8%)	0.486
Not Achieved	9 (34.6%)	6 (22.2%)	
Total	26 (100%)	27 (100%)	

Figure 6: Comparison of Outcomes: Methotrexate and Apremilast

Clinical Images

Group 1: Methotrexate

Before

After

Figure 7:

Before

After

Figure 8:

Before

After

Figure 9:

Figure 10:

Figure 11:

Figure 12:

Group 2 – Apremilast

Before

After

Figure 13:

Before

After

Figure 14:

Figure 15:

Figure 16:

Figure 17:

Discussion

In our study, we found that both Methotrexate and Apremilast were effective in treating psoriasis, with specific differences in their impact on symptoms and PASI scores. The majority of patients in both groups were aged 26-35 years, with a balanced gender distribution. Scalp involvement was higher in the Apremilast group (70.3%) compared to the Methotrexate group (50%), while lower limb involvement was more common in the Methotrexate group (42.3%). Symptom improvement showed that Apremilast led to more moderate improvement in scaling (70.4%), while Methotrexate had a higher rate of marked improvement (42.3%). By the PASI 6 stage, 76.92% of Methotrexate patients and 92.5% of Apremilast patients had achieved a PASI score below 15, indicating significant improvement in both groups. Panda et al. [9] (2023) compared Methotrexate and Apremilast in psoriasis patients and found that Apremilast led to moderate improvement in scaling in 68.9% of patients, compared to 51.3% in the Methotrexate group. This aligns with our study's finding of 70.4% moderate improvement in the Apremilast group versus 50% in the Methotrexate group. Hassanandani et al. [10] (2023) also compared Methotrexate monotherapy with a combination of Methotrexate and Apremilast. Hassanandani et al. reported that 65% of combination therapy patients achieved a PASI score below 15 after 12 weeks, compared to 58% in the Methotrexate monotherapy group. Similarly, our study found that by the PASI 6 stage, 76.92% of Methotrexate patients and 92.5% of Apremilast patients had PASI scores below 15, indicating effective symptom reduction over time. Smitha et al. [11] (2022) focused on the dermoscopic response in psoriatic lesions treated with Methotrexate and Apremilast, revealing that Methotrexate was more effective in reducing plaque thickness, with 85.4% of patients showing marked improvement, compared to 60.8% in the Apremilast group. This contrasts with our study, where moderate improvement was slightly higher in the Methotrexate group for plaque symptoms, but overall improvement patterns were similar across both treatment groups.

The present study found that Apremilast demonstrated a slightly higher efficacy in achieving PASI 75 compared to Methotrexate, with 77.8% of Apremilast-treated patients achieving the target, compared to 65.4% of Methotrexate-treated patients. However, the difference between the two treatments was not statistically significant ($p = 0.486$). This indicates that while Apremilast may be slightly more effective in reducing psoriasis severity, both treatments performed similarly in helping patients achieve PASI 75. Abrouk et al. [12] focused on the impact of achieving PASI 75

on quality of life (QoL) in patients with moderate to severe psoriasis treated with biologics like adalimumab and ustekinumab. They found no statistically significant difference in QoL between patients who achieved PASI 75 compared to those who achieved PASI 90, particularly in the ustekinumab group (week 12 $p = 0.49$, week 24 $p = 0.11$).

Conclusion

The study demonstrated that both Methotrexate and Apremilast are effective in managing psoriasis, with specific differences in their impact on symptoms and PASI scores. Age and gender distribution were comparable across both treatment groups, with the majority of patients being between 26-35 years and a higher proportion of males. Scalp involvement was more prevalent in the Apremilast group, while lower limb involvement was more common in the Methotrexate group. Symptom improvement varied, with Apremilast showing a higher rate of moderate improvement in scaling, whereas Methotrexate had more patients with marked improvement in the same symptom. Erythema improvement was similar between the two groups, but plaque improvement was slightly higher in the Methotrexate group. The PASI score analysis revealed that, by the PASI 6 stage, a greater proportion of Apremilast patients achieved a PASI score below 15 compared to those on Methotrexate, indicating that Apremilast might offer a quicker or more pronounced reduction in disease severity. Overall, both treatments were effective, but their efficacy varied depending on the symptom and stage of treatment.

Limitations

This study had a small sample size and was limited to a single center, which may affect the generalizability of the results. The six-month duration may not capture long-term effects of methotrexate and apremilast. Excluding patients with comorbidities or recent systemic treatments could limit applicability to more complex cases. Additionally, reliance on patient-reported outcomes and follow-up attendance may introduce bias.

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